

New European Bauhaus Academy

1st New European Bauhaus Academy Conference

Barcelona, February 27, 2026

Industrialized wood construction programme & prefab training school MaderAula

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NEBA South Hub Growth Success Story

What began as a small family of three organizations in two countries...

- Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia (Spain)
- Cesefor (Spain)
- Regione Liguria (Italy)

is now a community of 17 organizations in 5 countries!

- SocialTech Lab (Cyprus)
- Society and Urban Form Lab, University of Cyprus (Cyprus)
- C-MADE, University of Beira Interior (Portugal)
- KARMA Mixed Reality Lab, Koç Üniversitesi (Türkiye)
- Aks Creative Hub (Türkiye)
- Cluster Legno Arredo e Sistema Casa (Italy)
- Legno Servizi Forestry Cluster (Italy)
- Polytechnic Department of Engineering and Architecture, University of Udine (Italy)
- Department of Design, Polytechnic University of Milan (Italy)
- Technical Institute Academy Udine (Italy)
- Living Future Europe (Italy)
- University of Genoa (Italy)
- University of Florence (Italy)
- ART-ER Consortium Company (Italy)

Welcome!

NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 1

Formación continua para el sector
de la construcción

Modalidad híbrida
online y presencial

Programa Profesional en Edificación Industrializada con Madera

Accredited by the University of Leida

Student profile: architects, engineers,
property developers, investment funds, and
anyone interested in the field of timber
construction

7 weeks / 3 ECTS

Hybrid curriculum combining:

- Online classes and lectures
- In-person visits to forests,
factories and buildings

Website:

NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 1

Semana	Tipología	Tema
1	Seminario 1 PRESENCIAL	Introducción al diseño y construcción industrializado con madera Estrategias públicas de licitaciones y inversión inmobiliaria de bajas emisiones Visitas: Biblioteca Gabriel García Márquez, Terrazas para la Vida y Cirerers
2	Sesión 1 ONLINE	Técnicas 1: Estructuras 1 Procesos 1: BIM Caso de estudio (I): Edificio de viviendas Pisa, de Peris+Toral Arquitectes
3	Sesión 2 ONLINE	Técnicas 2: La acústica Procesos 2: Flujo de trabajo (Workflows) Caso de estudio (II): Edificio Hub Forestal Catalunya, de Bunyesc Arquitectes
4	Seminario 2 PRESENCIAL	La industrialización de la construcción en madera Visitas al bosque, al aserradero y a la planta de producción Visita a la fábrica de CLT
5	Sesión 3 ONLINE	Técnica 3: Estructuras 2 Procesos 3: Presupuestos y cálculo de emisiones Caso de estudio (III): Edificio de viviendas Our-Shelves, de SUMA Arquitectura
6	Sesión 4 ONLINE	Técnicas 4: Uniones y herrajes Procesos 4: Montaje de edificios de madera Caso de estudio (IV): Edificio de viviendas, de PMMT Arquitectura y O11h
7	Seminario 3 PRESENCIAL	Experiencia de montaje de estructuras de madera industrializada Elementos para el montaje de estructuras de CLT Entrega de diplomas y cóctel

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<https://iaac.net/masters/edificacion-industrializada-con-madera/>

NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 1

Programa Profesional en Edificación Industrializada con Madera

Global context

Faced with the climate emergency, we need transformative solutions for negative (or at least zero) emissions in our cities. Engineered timber has numerous characteristics that make it ideal for the transition to a sustainable circular bioeconomy, such as:

- Renewable source material
- Promotes sustainable forest management
- Stores CO₂
- Lightweight and easy to transport
- Is both a good insulator and a structural material
- Highly industrializable
- Promotes prefabrication for faster construction with greater control and precision, and less pollution and on-site risks

NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 1

Ciclo de vida de las construcciones de madera industrializadas

Programa Profesional en Edificación Industrializada con Madera

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NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 1

Invernadero Solar del Máster en Biocidades y Edificios Ecológicos Avanzados del IAAC en Valldaura Labs
construido con madera km 0.

Programa Profesional en Edificación Industrializada con Madera

Week 1: Seminar 1

14 hours

In-person in Catalonia

Day 1, Friday:

- Introduction to industrialized wood design and construction
- Public procurement strategies
- Low-emission real estate investment

NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 1

Programa Profesional en Edificación Industrializada con Madera

Week 1: Seminar 1

14 hours

In-person in Catalonia

Day 2, Saturday:

- Visit to the **Gabriel García Márquez Library**
- Visit to the **Terrazas para la Vida social housing building**
- Visit to the **Cirerers social housing building**

Week 2: Session 1

4.5 hours

Online

Day 3, Friday:

— Techniques 1: Structures 1

— Processes 1: BIM

— Case study I: Pisa residential building
by Peris+Torral Arquitectes

Análisis estructural de madera maciza y madera híbrida en el entorno del software S-TIMBER

NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 1

Techo de listones de madera utilizado para mejorar el rendimiento acústico en la Biblioteca Gabriel García Márquez, de SUMA Arquitectura.

Programa Profesional en Edificación Industrializada con Madera

Week 3: Session 2

4.5 hours

Online

Day 4, Friday:

— **Techniques 2: Acoustics**

— **Processes 2: Workflows**

— **Case study II: Hub Forestal Catalunya Building**
by Bunyesc Arquitectes

NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 1

Programa Profesional en Edificación Industrializada con Madera

Week 4: Seminar 2

14 hours

In-person in Galicia

Day 5, Thursday:

- **The industrialization of wood construction**
- Visit to a **forest**
- Visit to a **sawmill and a production plant**
- Visit to a **CLT factory**

Producción industrializada de CLT en Xilonor en Galicia

NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 1

Programa Profesional en Edificación Industrializada con Madera

Week 5: Session 3

4.5 hours

Online

Day 6, Friday:

— Techniques 3: Structures 2

— Processes 3: Budgeting and emissions calculations

— Case study III: Our-Shelves residential building by SUMA Arquitectura

Estudio comparativo de emisiones de gases de efecto invernadero para diferentes sistemas constructivos por Buro Happold.

NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 1

La ligereza y resistencia de la madera industrializada permite un rápido montaje de módulos prefabricados.

Programa Profesional en Edificación Industrializada con Madera

Week 6: Session 4

4.5 hours

Online

Day 8, Friday:

- **Techniques 4: Joints and Fittings**
- **Processes 4: Assembly of Timber Buildings**
- **Case Study IV: residential building**
by PMMT Arquitectura and O11h

NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 1

Programa Profesional en Edificación Industrializada con Madera

Week 7: Seminar 3

14 hours

In person in Catalonia

Day 9, Friday:

- **Modular prefabrication, connection hardware, and 3D-CAD/CAM software**
- **Lunch**
- **CLT panel manufacturing**

Una selección de sistemas de unión de Rothblaas

NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 1

Acto de graduación en los Valldaura Labs del IAAC

Programa Profesional en Edificación Industrializada con Madera

Week 7: Seminar 3

14 hours

In person in Catalonia

Day 10, Saturday:

— **Diplomas and cocktail**

1st edition launched in October, 2024

2nd edition launched in September, 2025

46 trainees to date!

NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 2

Programas prácticos de acción rápida en Edificación Industrializada con Madera

Timber Frame 35 h.

CLT 35 h.

Multi-storey 49 h.

Cladding 35 h.

CONTINUOUS TRAINING

Mastering industrialized timber construction methods to transform the industry.

On-site Hands-on Courses:

"learning by doing" training for all construction systems, covering every stage of the building process. Students are provided with a range of construction materials, as well as wood cutting and machining tools, to **manufacture a complete prototype.**

Online Courses:

We offer an **adapted and flexible format** designed to reach the widest range of professionals. These courses are structured into three core modules: **design, structural analysis, and prefabrication & assembly.**

Free Webinars:

Free **themed webinars** covering the latest in industrialised timber construction, showcasing the best of the sector in Spain and Latin America each month.

NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 2

Curso ONLINE diseño,
cálculo y prefabricación y
montaje con Entramad

del 3 de marzo al 23 de junio
Online

por Club Madera en MADERAULA

Programas prácticos de acción rápida en Edificación Industrializada con Madera

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WEBINARS: The Open Academy for Timber Construction.

mader aula 26.09.24 17.30 h

Webinar

Monográfico

Construcción actual con madera (1)

- Edificio T3 Diagonal
- Edificio Hyperion
- Rehabilitación de 7 alturas en Andorra

mader aula 10.10.24 17.30 h

Webinar

Monográfico

Con madera, con salud

- Salud Ambiental y Edificación
- Arquitectura como herramienta de Salud Pública
- Proyecto Creixem Jugant
- Proyecto Centro de Salud y PAC de A Laracha

mader aula 07.11.24 17.30 h

Webinar

Monográfico

¿Tenemos suficiente madera para construir?

- Juan Picos: Profesor del Departamento de Ingeniería de los Recursos Naturales y Medio Ambiente de la Universidad de Vigo.
- José Luis Villanueva: Director de transferencia del Área de Industria y Construcción en Cieslor.
- Gabriel A. Gutiérrez Tejeda: Asesor de la Dirección General de Política Forestal y Biodiversidad en la Junta de Andalucía.
- Lidia Guitart Xarpell: Gerente de la Asociación de propietarios del Monteviege y el Corredor.

mader aula 19.12.24 17.30 h (GTM +1)

Webinar

Monográfico

Contextualización de la construcción con madera en Iberoamérica

Introducción a cargo de Vanesa Baño (InnovaWood)

- Alexandra Sosa Zitto, Universidad Tecnológica Nacional (Argentina)
- Carillo Cilli Jr, Universidad de São Paulo (Brasil)
- Alexander Igor Opazo, Universidad Bio Bio (Chile)
- Laura Moya, Universidad ORT (Uruguay)
- Jorge Gonçalves Branco, Universidade do Minho (Portugal)

mader aula 23.01.25 17.30 h

Webinar

Monográfico

Diseñando con madera paso a paso

- Nacho Lechón (Abatón Arquitectura)
- José María Quirós (Andas Homes)
- Julen Pérez Santisteban (Wagh Thistleton Architects)
- Jorge Blasco (Estudi m103)

mader aula 20.02.25 17.30 h

Webinar

Monográfico

Construcción actual con madera (2)

- Oceana Research Lab (Borja Soriano)
- Escuela de Música Zumarte en Usurbil (Maialen Sagarna)
- Comisaría de Policía Local de Olesa de Montserrat (Iván Pérez Barés)

NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 2

Año	Mes	Tipo de actividad	CCAA	Localidad	Público Alcanzado	
1.	2025	Marzo	Curso Presencial	Andalucía	Malaga	17
2.	2025	Marzo	Curso Online	Online	Online	58
3.	2024	Junio	Curso Presencial	Madrid	Madrid	10
4.	2024	Marzo	Curso Online	Online	Online	185
5.	2024	Marzo	Curso Presencial	Castilla y León	Soria	12
6.	2024	Julio	Curso Presencial	Castilla y León	Revena	24
7.	2024	Noviembre	Curso Presencial	Cataluña	Balsareny	13
8.	2024	Septiembre	Curso Presencial	Galicia	Santiago de Compos...	34
9.	2024	Febrero	Curso Online	Online	Online	44
10.	2024	Octubre	Curso Online	Online	Online	76
11.	2024	Octubre	Curso Presencial	Cataluña	Ohvan	9
12.	2023	Octubre	Curso Presencial	Madrid	Madrid	21
13.	2023	Diciembre	Curso Presencial	Andalucía	Málaga	7
14.	2023	Septiembre	Curso Online	Online	Online	12

On-site course locations and outreach.

Note: Figures are continuously growing; as of February 2025, nearly 1,000 students have already gained expertise in industrialized construction.)

Programas prácticos de acción rápida en Edificación Industrializada con Madera

TRAINING

Through **Maderaula**, Cesefor has trained over **850** students across its online and in-person formats— including **400** participants in our hands-on programs from sept. 2023.

These professionals are introduced to **industrialized timber construction** and the use of **bio-based materials**, internalizing a construction culture defined by sustainability, efficiency, and industrial precision.

TRAINING HUBS

In 2026, the Maderaula Training Hubs will also be launched. Their goal is to achieve a **multiplier effect in workforce training** across the sector, ensuring the lowest possible investment and the most cost-effective learning curve.

-Spanish speaking **american countries** are included within the effort of **knowledge transfer and exchange**

NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 2

Maderaula-LAB a Timber Construction training programs Laboratory

The building

We are building a **laboratory** aimed at training the bio-based industrialised prefabricated construction industry to **train professionals in the practical phases of any project in a safe environment:**

- Manufacture of technological products.
- Structural CNC
- Automatic assembly line
- Training in high-rise construction up to 3 floors on a 1:1 scale

These facilities will be at the service of the **industry, our academic and vocational training partners at NEBA South-HUB** for the design and development of any **training programme prototype.**

NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 2

Maderaula-LAB a Timber Construction training programs Laboratory

Embedded training

Each Clubmadera project is an **opportunity to teach, inspire and convince** the construction sector that there is a **better way** of doing things, a **more humane** way of facing the challenges of future housing and civil infrastructure.

Through the Maderaula LAB implementation project, whose **structure is FSC-certified** throughout its value chain, we have managed to train **nearly 80 people** in the various free practical classroom courses that have been held.

“Make the most of every opportunity as the journey should not be the only reward”

NEBA South Hub Training Success Story 2

PROMOTORES

SOCIOS

COLABORADORES

Authored and operated:

In collaboration with:

A public-private effort to promote the transition to green building

Acknowledgements

Only by working together can the entire industry achieve **true transformation**, moving towards a **transition** that will give our forests and rural areas a better future.

The **credit** for our successes lies with the **trust** placed in us **by our partners** and their annual non-refundable contributions.

Cesefor is able to promote this training, dissemination and awareness programme **thanks to the fundamental support of its patrons**, particularly the **Provincial Council of Soria**.

